

Exploring translation methods, strategies and procedures used to overcome linguistic problems in translating proverbs from English into Arabic

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ABSTRACT

This Paper aims to explore effective translation methods used in translating proverbs from English into Arabic. To achieve this goal, the researcher points out three hypothesis. Firstly, linguistic problems resulting from proverb translation have direct effect on translator's ability to find correct equivalents. Secondly, translators do not effectively deal with Linguistic problems when translating proverbs from English into Arabic, and thirdly, the novice translators lack abilities in utilizing translation methods, strategies and procedures. A questionnaire survey for English Language and translation teachers; 54 of them responded to a questionnaire composed of 22 items representing the main hypotheses of the study. The study revealed that Linguistic problems and difficulties are not effectively dealt with by translators in rend proverbs from English into Arabic. The study also revealed that most of translators are not familiar with the effective translation methods and procedures related to proverb translation and idiomatic expressions. Based on the findings of the current study, the researcher recommends that proverbs translators should perhaps be given much more translation practice in general and practical exercises in proverbial expressions to help them to identify the most appropriate translation methods and procedures that best suit the text types, culture-based sayings and idiomatic expressions. Prior to that, courses in theories of translation and translation methods, in particular, are ought to be introduced when designing and preparing course specifications of the related subjects. That would help translators to overcome the linguistic difficulties and problems of proverb translation and hence, produce correct versions in the target language i.e. the Arabic one.

Introduction

Translation is a vital tool for bridging linguistic and cultural gaps, enabling the exchange of ideas, knowledge, and literary developments across different languages and cultures. As Webster's Dictionary (2001:2011) defines, translation is "the rendering of something into another language or into one's own from another language." It plays a crucial role in fostering integration on both national and international levels, allowing for the communication of significant historical events and cultural revolutions through various languages (Khan, 2013:47).

The translation process is an interdisciplinary activity that demands proficiency in both the source language (SL) and target language (TL), as well as a deep understanding of cultural, linguistic, and communication nuances. Nida (2006:11) emphasizes that translation is not a standalone science but rather a specialized skill requiring aesthetic sensitivity and a broad knowledge base, including linguistics, cultural anthropology, philology, psychology, and communication theories. The primary goal of translation, as stated in Wikipedia, is to convey

the meaning of a text from the source language into an equivalent text in the target language.

Proverbs, as culture-based sayings and idiomatic expressions, present unique challenges in translation due to their non-literal meanings, cultural specificity, and use of archaic language. Translating proverbs from English into Arabic is particularly challenging due to the linguistic and cultural differences between these languages. Achieving accurate equivalence in translating proverbs requires not only linguistic skills but also an understanding of the cultural contexts that shape these expressions. This study explores the methods, strategies, and procedures used by translators to overcome the linguistic problems encountered in translating English proverbs into Arabic.

The importance of translating proverbs lies in their ability to convey complex ideas succinctly, filling gaps in linguistic expressions and enriching communication. However, the lexical, stylistic, and cultural differences between English and Arabic make this task challenging. The demand for effective translation methods and procedures has long been of interest to both professional and novice translators. Understanding and applying

the appropriate methods and strategies in proverb translation are crucial for achieving accurate and culturally relevant translations.

According to Newmark (1988), translation methods pertain to the translation of entire texts, while translation procedures apply to sentences and smaller linguistic units. In the context of translating proverbs, various strategies and procedures are employed to overcome the inherent linguistic challenges. Gazala (1995:38) categorizes proverbs into three groups based on their equivalence in translation: absolute equivalence, similar equivalence, and different equivalence. Each category presents distinct challenges and requires specific strategies to achieve accurate translations. Similarly, Baker (1992:65) outlines four strategies for translating idioms and fixed expressions, which can also be applied to proverbs.

This study aims to explore and analyze the strategies and methods used in translating proverbs from English into Arabic. By identifying the most effective translation methods, the study seeks to contribute to the field of translation studies, particularly in the area of proverb translation, and to provide practical insights for translators, learners, and educators. The significance of the study lies in its potential to enhance the understanding of proverb translation, thereby improving the quality and accuracy of translations in this challenging area.

Methodology

This study adopts a Descriptive Analytical Method to examine the methods and procedures used to overcome linguistic challenges in translating proverbs from English into Arabic. The researcher aimed to gather insights from English language lecturers and translators at various educational institutions regarding their perspectives on effective translation strategies for proverbs.

Sampling procedures

The study population consists of English language teachers, many of whom possess both theoretical and practical experience in translation. A purposive sample of 54 respondents, comprising both male and female participants, was selected to participate in the study. These respondents completed a questionnaire that included 22 items

organized into three main sections, each addressing different aspects of proverb translation and related methods.

Instruments of the study

The primary data collection tool used in this study is a questionnaire. This instrument was designed to capture both quantitative and qualitative data, utilizing a 5-point Likert scale (ranging from 1 to 5) to assess the views and opinions of respondents. The questionnaire was specifically crafted to gather information on the effectiveness of translation methods and procedures used in translating proverbs from English into Arabic. It was administered to English language and translation teachers with sufficient experience in the field.

The questionnaire is divided into three main sections:

First Part: Includes seven statements exploring the factors contributing to the challenges in translating the meaning of proverbs.

Second Part: Contains seven statements examining the impact of translation competence on the accuracy of rendering proverbs from English into Arabic.

Third Part: Comprises eight statements focusing on the identification and adoption of translation methods in translating proverbs from English into Arabic.

Validity and reliability of instruments

To ensure the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, the researcher consulted a group of academic experts, including university professors, who provided feedback on the questions, form, and content of the instrument. Their recommendations were instrumental in refining the questionnaire to better achieve the research objectives.

After validating the content, the reliability of the questionnaire was tested using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 17). The "split-half" method was employed, where the questions were divided into two groups: odd-numbered and even-numbered questions. The correlation between these two halves was calculated, and the reliability coefficients of Spearman-Brown and Pearson were determined.

The resulting reliability score of 0.93 indicates that the questionnaire is highly reliable.

Data collection and analysis

Data were collected through the administered questionnaire, and the responses were analyzed and classified. Frequencies and percentages of the responses were calculated, and the data were subsequently analyzed, narrated, and described in line with the study's objectives.

Procedure

The research process involved several key steps, beginning with a review of theoretical literature and empirical studies relevant to the topic. A questionnaire was then designed specifically for English language teachers and translators, which was subsequently presented to a panel of experts for validation and reliability assessment. After validation, the questionnaire was distributed to the selected sample, and the collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods.

Results and Discussion

Description of research sample

The samples respondents were classified as Gender, Age, Qualification, Experience, Trainer in translation and Trainer as part-time services (Table 1).

Table 1: Description of the samples

Characteristics	Frequency	Percent	
Gender	Male	47	87.0
	Female	7	13.0
Age	35-45	31	57.4
	46-55	20	37.0
	more	3	5.6
Qualification	B.A	3	5.6
	M.A	29	53.7
	PH.D	22	40.7
Experience	less than one year	14.8	8
	1-5years	85.2	46
	more	-	-
Trainer in translation	Yes	28	51.9
	No	26	48.1
Trainer as part-time	Yes	32	59.3
	No	22	40.7

The questionnaire results

In the questionnaire, EFL and translation teachers are asked to complete a questionnaire by answering 22 enclosed questions. Results of the questionnaire are presented in the tables below (2-4). Each questionnaire item is displayed discussed and then verified according to the research hypotheses to show the significances and correlations, if any.

Table 2: Proverb translation of meaning is problematic due to the following factors

No	Mean	Std. Deviation	Responses	Frequency	Percent	t	df	Sig	reality of	Value
1	4.5769	.61410	Strongly disagree	0	0	22.679	77	.001	significance	Strongly agree
			Disagree	1	1.3					
			Neutral	2	2.6					
			Agree	26	33.3					
			Strongly agree	49	62.8					
2	4.3077	.91606	Strongly disagree	2	2.6	12.608	77	.001	significance	Strongly agree
			Disagree	0	0					
			Neutral	12	15.4					
			Agree	22	28.2					
			Strongly agree	42	53.8					
3	4.0256	.86751	Strongly disagree	1	1.3	10.442	77	.001	significance	agree
			Disagree	4	5.1					
			Neutral	10	12.8					
			Agree	40	51.3					
			Strongly agree	23	29.5					
4	4.3846	.74260	Strongly disagree	0	0	16.467		.001	significance	Strongly agree

			Disagree	2	2.6				
			Neutral	6	7.7		77		
			Agree	30	38.5				
			Strongly agree	40	51.3				
			Strongly disagree	0	0				
5	4.2949	.75780	Disagree	1	1.3	15.091	77	.001 significance	Strongly agree
			Neutral	11	14.1				
			Agree	30	38.5				
			Strongly agree	36	46.2				
			Strongly disagree	0	0				
6	4.4103	.72856	Disagree	2	2.6	17.095	77	.001 significance	Strongly agree
			Neutral	5	6.4				
			Agree	30	38.5				
			Strongly agree	41	52.6				
			Strongly disagree	0	0				
7	4.2821	.70060	Disagree	1	1.3	16.161	77	.001 significance	Strongly agree
			Neutral	8	10.3				
			Agree	37	47.4				
			Strongly agree	32	41.0				

(Item No. 1) Misunderstanding the meaning of the proverb results in incorrect rendition of it:

Based on the data presented in the table 2, it shows that almost all of the respondents (96.1%) agreed and strongly agreed that misunderstanding the meaning of the proverb results in the incorrect rendition of it .The frequencies are (26), (49); they constitute 33.3% and 62%, the total is 96.1%. This means that most of the respondents believe that that misunderstanding the meaning of the proverb results in the incorrect rendition of it.

As seen from the table 2, the value of (T. test) calculated (22.679) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical reality conclusion of the phrase which says that misunderstanding the meaning of the proverb results in incorrect rendition of it. According to the reality of the statistical inference above, the subjects' approval of this phrase is at a very high significance level of (0.05).

(Item No. 2). Some English words have no direct counterpart in the Arabic language:

It is observed from this table 2 that most of the respondents (82%) agreed and strongly agreed some English words have no direct counterpart in the Arabic language. The frequencies are (22), (42); they constitute 28.2% and 53.8%, the total is 82%. This means that most of the respondents agreed that some English words have no direct counterpart in the Arabic language.

It is clear from the table 2, the value of (T. test) calculated (12.608) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical reality conclusion of the phrase which says that some English words have no direct counterpart in the Arabic language. As seen from the reality of statistical inference, the subjects approve this phrase moderately at high significance level of (0.05).

(Item No. 3). Some English proverbs may have equivalents in Arabic that are similar in form but different in meaning:

The table 2 shows that many of respondents (80%) agreed and strongly agreed that some English proverbs may have equivalents in Arabic that are similar in form but different in meaning. The frequencies are (40), (23); they constitute 51.3% and 29.5 %, the total is 80%. This means that many of the respondents believe that some English proverbs may have equivalents in Arabic that are similar in form but different in meaning.

The table 2 shows that, the value of (T. test) calculated (10.442) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical reality conclusion of the phrase which says that Some English proverbs may have equivalents in Arabic that are similar in form but different in meaning language. Seen from the reality of statistical inference, the subjects

approval of this phrase moderately at significance level of (0.05).

(Item No 4) Some proverbs comprise cultured-based meaning of context that need to be well understood and then translated:

It is observed from this table 2 that most of respondents (89.9%) agreed and strongly agreed that some proverbs comprise cultured-based meaning of context that need to be well understood and then translated. The frequencies are (30), (40); they constitute 38.5% and 51.3 %, the total is 80%. This means that most of the respondents believe that some proverbs comprise cultured-based meaning of context that needs pragmatics to be understood and then translated. It is clear from the table 2, the value of (T. test) calculated (16.467) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical reality conclusion of the phrase which says that some proverbs comprise cultured-based meaning of context that need to be well understood and then translated. As seen from the reality of statistical inference, the subjects approve this phrase moderately at high significance level of (0.05).

(Item No 5) English proverb translating needs pragmatic and context background:

The table shows that most of respondents (84.7.9%) agreed and strongly agreed that English proverbs translating needs pragmatic context background. The frequencies are (30), (36); they constitute 38.5% and 46.2 %, the total is 84.7%. This means that most of the respondents believe that English proverb translating needs pragmatic and context background.

It is clear from the table 2, that the value of (T. test) calculated (15.091) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that English proverb translating needs pragmatic context background . As seen from the reality of statistical inference, the subjects approve this phrase moderately at significance level of (0.05).

(Item No 6) When given in a context, a translator must choose the most suitable equivalent to convey the nuance of the text:

The table 2 shows that many of respondents (74.7.9%) agreed and strongly agreed that when given in a context, a translator must choose the most suitable equivalent to convey the nuance of the text. The frequencies are (30), (41); they constitute 38.5% and 52.6 %, the total is 74.7%. This means that many of the respondents believe that when given in a context, a translator must choose the most suitable equivalent to convey the nuance of the text.

According to from the table above, the value of (T. test) calculated (16.467) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the reality of statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that when given in a context, a translator must choose the most suitable equivalent to convey the nuance of the text. As seen from the reality of statistical inference, the subjects approve this phrase moderately at high significance level of (0.05).

(Item No 7) Misinterpretation of the intended message of metaphorical proverbial expressions disturbs the proverb rendition.

It is observed from the table above that most of respondents (88.4%) agreed and strongly agreed that misinterpretation of the intended message of metaphorical proverbial expressions disturbs the proverb rendition. The frequencies are (37), (32); they constitute 47.4% and 41. %, the total is 88.4%. This means that most of the respondents view that when given in a context, a translator must choose the most suitable equivalent to convey the nuance of the text.

As seen from the table 2, the value of (T. test) calculated (16.467) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the reality of statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that misinterpretation of the intended message of metaphorical proverbial expressions disturbs the proverb rendition. Seen from the reality of statistical inference, the subjects approval of this phrase is at high significance level of (0.05).

Table 3: Translation competence affects the rendering of proverbs:

						Test Value=3				
No	Mean	Std. Deviation	Responses	Frequency	Percent	t	df	Sig	reality of 0.05	Value
8	4.5000	.65959	Strongly disagree	0	0	20.085	77	.001	significance	Strongly agree
			Disagree	0	0					
			Neutral	7	9.0					
			Agree	25	32.1					
			Strongly agree	46	59.0					
9	4.0513	.71890	Strongly disagree	0	0	12.915	77	.001	significance	agree
			Disagree	1	1.3					
			Neutral	15	19.2					
			Agree	41	52.6					
			Strongly agree	21	26.9					
10	4.1154	.85251	Strongly disagree	0	0	11.555	77	.001	significance	agree
			Disagree	2	2.6					
			Neutral	18	23.1					
			Agree	27	34.6					
			Strongly agree	31	39.7					
11	3.7564	.88547	Strongly disagree	0	0	7.545	77	.001	significance	agree
			Disagree	8	10.3					
			Neutral	18	23.1					
			Agree	37	47.4					
			Strongly agree	15	19.2					
12	3.7308	.80054	Strongly disagree	1	1.3	8.062	77	.001	significance	agree
			Disagree	2	2.6					
			Neutral	26	33.3					
			Agree	37	47.4					
			Strongly agree	12	15.4					
13	4.2179	.78372	Strongly disagree	0	0	13.725	77	.001	significance	Strongly agree
			Disagree	3	3.8					
			Neutral	8	10.3					
			Agree	36	46.2					
			Strongly agree	31	39.7					
14	4.4231	.82995	Strongly disagree	1	1.3	15.143	77	.001	significance	Strongly agree
			Disagree	2	2.6					
			Neutral	5	6.4					
			Agree	25	32.1					
			Strongly agree	45	57.7					

(Item No. 8) Words related to culture is considered problematic to novice translators in their task as a major linguistic difficulty in proverb translation

As shown from the table 3, most of respondents (91%) agreed and strongly agreed that words related to culture is considered problematic to novice translators in their task as a major linguistic difficulty in proverb translation. The frequencies are (25), (46); they constitute 32.1% and 59. %, the total is 91%. This means that most of the respondents view that when given in a

context, a translator must choose the most suitable equivalent to convey the nuance of the text.

Seen from the table 3, the value of (T. test) calculated (20.085) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the reality of statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that words related to culture is considered problematic to novice translators in their task as a major linguistic difficulty in proverb translation It is clear from the reality of statistical inference, that the subjects approval of this phrase is at high significance level of (0.05).

(Item No .9) - Proverb sayings may encompass unfamiliar word for students:

The table 3 shows that many of respondents (79.5%) agreed and strongly agreed that proverb sayings may encompass unfamiliar word for students. The frequencies are (41), (21); they constitute 52.6% and 26.9%, the total is 79.57%. This means that many of the respondents believe that proverb sayings may encompass unfamiliar word for students.

As seen from the table 3, the value of (T. test) calculated (12.915) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the reality of statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that proverb sayings may encompass unfamiliar word for students. It is clear from the statistical inference reality, that the subjects approved this phrase at a moderately significance level of (0.05.)

(Item No. 10) Proverbs translation requires skills in using language resources such as dictionaries to verify accurate word meaning:

It is observed from the table 3 that many of respondents (74.3%) agreed and strongly agreed that Proverbs translation requires skills in using language resources such as dictionaries to verify accurate word meaning. The frequencies are (27),(31); they constitute 34.6% and 26.9 % , the total is 74,3 %. This means that most of the respondents believe that proverbs translation requires skills in using language resources such as dictionaries to verify accurate word meaning.

According to from the table 3, the value of (T. test) calculated (11.555) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the reality of statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that proverbs translation requires skills in using language resources such as dictionaries to verify accurate word meaning. As seen from the reality of statistical inference, the subjects approve this phrase moderately at high significance level of (0.05).

(Item No. 11) Novice translators may be hindered by factors of carelessness and time pressure:

Based on the data presented in the table 3, a lot of respondents (66.3%) agreed and strongly agreed that novice translators may be hindered by factors of carelessness and time pressure. The frequencies are (37), (15); they constitute 47.4% and 19.2 %, the total is 66,6%. This means that a lot of respondents view that proverbs translation requires skills in using language resources such as dictionaries to verify accurate word meaning.

It is clear from the table 3, that the value of (T. test) calculated (7.545) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that novice translators may be hindered by factors of carelessness and time pressure. As seen from the reality of statistical inference, the subjects approve this phrase moderately at significance level of (0.05)

(Item No. 12) - The incapability to produce versions of Arabic proverbs, or the inability to understand the English ones, affects proverb translation:

According to the data presented in the table 3, a lot of respondents (62.8%) agreed and strongly agreed that the in capability to produce versions of Arabic proverbs, or the inability to understand the English ones, affect proverb translation. The frequencies are (37), (12); they constitute 47.4% and 15.4 %, the total is 62.8%. This means that a lot of respondents believe that the incapability to produce versions of Arabic proverbs, or the inability to understand the English ones, affect proverb translation.

As seen from the table 3, that the value of (T. test) calculated (8.062) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that that the incapability to produce versions of Arabic proverbs, or the inability to understand the English ones, affect proverb translation. It is obvious from the statistical inference that the subjects approval of the phrase is moderately at significance level of (0.05).

(Item No. 13) -The linguistic differences between the SL and the TL languages i.e. the English and Arabic languages cause problems of fully understanding the intended meaning of proverbs:

Based on data presented in the table 3, most of the respondents (85.9%) agreed and strongly agreed that the linguistic differences between the SL and the TL languages i.e. the English and Arabic languages cause problems of understanding the intended meaning. The frequencies are (36), (13); they constitute 46.2% and 39.7%, the total is 85.9%. This means that many of respondents believe that the linguistic differences between the SL and the TL languages i.e. the English and Arabic languages cause problems of understanding the intended meaning of the proverb.

Seen from the table 3, that the value of (T. test) calculated (13.725) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that the linguistic differences between the SL and the TL languages i.e. the English and Arabic languages cause problems of understanding the intended meaning of the proverb. It is clear from the statistical inference, that the subjects approval of the phrase is moderately at significance level of (0.05).

(Item No. 14) – A strong knowledge of SL culture and TL culture facilitates the rendering of proverbs:

The table 3 shows that most of the respondents (89.8%) agreed and strongly agreed that a strong knowledge of SL culture and TL culture facilitates the rendering of proverbs. The frequencies are (25), (45); they constitute 32.1% and 57.7%, the total is 89.9%. This means that many of respondents believe strong knowledge of SL culture and TL culture facilitates the rendering of proverbs.

As seen from the table 3, that the value of (T. test) calculated (15.143) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that a strong knowledge of SL culture and TL culture facilitates the rendering of proverbs.. It is obvious from the statistical inference that the subjects approval of the phrase is moderately at significance level of (0.05).

Table 4: The Identification and utilization of Translation Methods and Procedures in Translating Proverbs from English into Arabic:

No.	Mean	Std. Deviation	Responses	Frequency Percent		Test Value=3			Value	
				t	df	Sig	reality of			
15	4.3718	.56082	Strongly disagree	0	0	21.603	77	.001	significance	Strongly agree
			Disagree	0	0					
			Neutral	3	3.8					
			Agree	43	55.1					
			Strongly agree	32	41.0					
16	3.7308	.98920	Strongly disagree	1	1.3	6.524	77	.001	significance	agree
			Disagree	9	11.5					
			Neutral	18	23.1					
			Agree	32	41.0					
			Strongly agree	18	23.1					
17	4.1923	.75692	Strongly disagree	0	0	13.912	77	.001	significance	agree
			Disagree	0	0					
			Neutral	16	20.5					
			Agree	31	39.7					
			Strongly agree	31	39.7					
18	4.1923	.80675	Strongly disagree	1	1.3	13.053	77	.001	significance	agree
			Disagree	1	1.3					
			Neutral	10	12.8					
			agree	36	46.2					
			Strongly agree	30	38.5					
19	3.5513	1.25509	Strongly disagree	5	6.4	3.879	77	.001	significance	agree
			Disagree	13	16.7					
			Neutral	17	21.8					

			Agree	20	25.6				
			Strongly agree	23	29.5				
			Strongly disagree	2	2.6				
			Disagree	1	1.3				
20	4.1923	.91251	Neutral	11	14.1	11.540	77	.001	significance agree
			Agree	30	38.5				
			Strongly agree	34	43.6				
			Strongly disagree	3	3.8		77	.001	significance agree
			disagree	11	14.1				
21	3.5897	1.11000	neutral	19	24.4	4.692			
			agree	27	34.6				
			Strongly agree	18	23.1				
			Strongly disagree	3	3.8				
			Disagree	2	2.6				
22	4.0000	.93974	Neutral	10	12.8	9.398	77	.001	significance agree
			Agree	40	51.3				
			Strongly agree	23	29.5				

(Item No.15) - A translator must find ways to overcome linguistic problems when translating English proverb:

According to the data presented in the table 4, almost all of respondents (96%) agreed and strongly agreed that a translator must find ways to overcome linguistic problems when translating English proverb. The frequencies are (43), (32); they constitute 55.1% and 41% the total is 97 %. This means that a lot of respondents agreed a translator must find ways to overcome linguistic problems when translating English proverb.

As observed from the table 4, that the value of (T. test) calculated (21.603) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that a translator must find ways to overcome linguistic problems when translating English proverb. It is obvious from the statistical inference, that the subjects approval of the phrase is moderately at very high significance level of (0.05).

(Item No.16): Not all of strategies are of the same benefit to proverb translation:

According to the data presented in the table 4, many of respondents (64.1%) agreed and strongly agreed that not all of strategies are of the same benefit to proverb translation. The frequencies are (32),(18); they constitute 41.1% and 23 % ,the total is 64 %. This means that a lot of respondents

agreed that not all of strategies are of the same benefit to proverb translation.

As observed from the table 4, that the value of (T. test) calculated (6.524) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that not all of strategies are of the same benefit to proverb translation.. It is obvious from the statistical inference that the subjects approval of the phrase is moderately at very high significance level of (0.05).

(Item No.17)- It is the role of the translator to sort out what strategies that best suit the text translation to pursuit a good translation of proverbs:

As seen from the data presented in the table 4, many of respondents (79.4%) agreed and strongly agreed that it is the role of the translator to sort out what strategies that best suit the text translation to pursuit a good translation of proverbs. The frequencies are (31), (31); they constitute 39.7% and 39.7 % ,the total is 79.4 % . This means that many of respondents agreed that it is the role of the translator to sort out what strategies that suit the text translation to pursuit a good translation of proverbs.

As observed from the table 4, that the value of (T. test) calculated (13.912) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance

from the statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that it is the role of the translator to sort out what strategies that suit the text translation to pursuit a good translation of proverbs. It is clear from the statistical inference that the subjects approval of the phrase is moderately at high significance level of (0.05).

(Item No.18)- The most effective translation method is to find the correct proverb equivalent in the target language (TL).

As observed from the data presented in the table 4, most of respondents (84.4%) agreed and strongly agreed that the most effective translation method is to find the correct proverb equivalent in the target language (TL). The frequencies are (36), (30); they constitute 46.2% and 38.5%, the total is 84.4 %. This means that a lot of respondents agreed that the most effective translation method is to find the correct proverb equivalent in the target language (TL).

As observed from the table 4, that the value of (T. test) calculated (13.053) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that the most effective translation method is to find the correct proverb equivalent in the target language (TL). It is obvious from the statistical inference that the subjects approval of the phrase is moderately a high significance level of (0.05).

(Item No.19)- The literal translation method conveys the meaning of the proverb:

As observed from the data presented in the table 4, only some of respondents (55.1%) agreed and strongly agreed that the literal translation method conveys the meaning of the proverb. The frequencies are (20), (23); they constitute 25.6% and 29.5%, the total is 55.1%. This means that only some of respondents agreed that the literal translation method conveys the meaning of the proverb.

Seen from the table 4, that the value of (T. test) calculated (3.879) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that the literal translation method conveys the meaning of the proverb.. It is obvious from the statistical inference, that the subjects approval of

the phrase is moderately a high significance level of (0.05).

(Item No. 20) - lack of knowledge or unfamiliarity with translation techniques and strategies cause obstacles for translators:

The table 4 shows that most of respondents (82.1%) agreed and strongly agreed that lack of knowledge or unfamiliarity with translation techniques and strategies cause obstacles for translators. The frequencies are (30), (34); they constitute 38.5% and 43.6%, the total is 82.1%. This means that many of respondents agreed that lack of knowledge or unfamiliarity with translation techniques and strategies cause obstacles for translators.

As seen from the table 4, that the value of (T. test) calculated (11.540) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that lack of knowledge or unfamiliarity with translation techniques and strategies cause obstacles for translators . It is observed from the statistical inference, that the subjects approval of the phrase is moderately at a high significance level of (0.05).

(Item No. 21)- the non-figurative meaning of the proverb could be stated straight forwardly:

The table 4 clearly shows that only some of respondents (57.7%) agreed and strongly agreed that the non-figurative meaning of the proverb could be stated straight forwardly. The frequencies are (27), (18); they constitute 34.6% and 23.1%, the total is 57.7%. This means that only some of respondents agreed that the non-figurative meaning of the proverb could be stated straight forwardly.

Seen from the table 4, that the value of (T. test) calculated (4.692) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical conclusion of the phrase which says that the non-figurative meaning of the proverb could be stated straight forwardly. It is observed from the statistical inference, that the subjects approval of the phrase is moderately a high significance level of (0.05).

(Item No. 22) - If a translator doesn't find equivalent in target language (TL), he/she has

to translate the proverb translation of meaning i.e. (communicative translation):

The table 4 shows that most of respondents (80.8%) agreed and strongly agreed that if a translator doesn't find equivalent in target language (TL), he/she has to translate the proverb translation of meaning i.e. (communicative translation). The frequencies are (40), (23); they constitute 51.3% and 29.5%, the total is 80.8%. This means that most of respondents agreed that if a translator doesn't find equivalent in target language (TL), he/she has to translate the proverb translation of meaning i.e. (communicative translation).

As seen from the table 4, that the value of (T. test) calculated (9.398) with a degree of freedom (77) and the value of the probability is (.001), which means that there is a statistical significance from the statistical conclusion of the phrase which says if a translator doesn't find equivalent in target language (TL), he/she has to translate the proverb translation of meaning i.e. (communicative translation). It is observed from the statistical inference, that the subjects approval of the phrase is moderately at high significance level of (0.05). Discussion and conclusion of questionnaire Results:

The results of the questionnaire are presented in the tables 2- 4). Each item was discussed separately to show the type of linguistic difficulty faced by translators according to the teachers' views. According to the data analysis shown in the tables above, the most significant findings revealed by the study are the following:

It is obvious from the results that items number (1, 4, 7, 5, 2) whose score are arranged in descending order have the highest scores in giving positive answers (agree and strongly) supporting the first hypothesis which says that Linguistic difficulties resulting from literal and non-literal meaning in English proverb have direct effects on the translator's ability to find words and equivalents when translating proverbs into Arabic Language. Moreover, questionnaire items number

(8 , 14 , 13, 9) whose scores are arranged in a descending order have the highest scores in supporting the second hypothesis (agree and strongly agree) that Linguistic difficulties are not effectively dealt with by translators in translating proverbs from English into Arabic .In addition to that, the items number (15,18, 20,22) which show that respondents believe that the novice translators lack abilities in utilizing translation methods and procedures to deal with the problem of linguistic difficulties arising when rendering proverbs from English into Arabic: Nevertheless, there are only few items whose scores are arranged in ascending order have the least scores in the questionnaire answers such as items number (19, 21 and 12) mainly in the second and the third hypotheses.

These three items strongly support the notion regarding the identification and utilization of the effective translation methods and procedures when rendering proverbs from English into Arabic.

Verifications of the study hypothesis

This provides the results of the following questions:

- 1-To what extent do linguistic problems and difficulties affect the translation of proverbs from English into Arabic?
2. In what ways are such linguistic difficulties dealt with in the English/Arabic translation of proverbs?
- 3 To what extend are novice translators able to utilize translation methods and procedures in translating proverbs from English into Arabic??

Verifications of the questionnaire results

Results Related to the First Hypothesis

Linguistic problems, difficulties, and problem resulting from translating of proverbs from English into Arabic have direct effects on the translator's ability to find words and equivalents when translating proverbs into Arabic Language.

Table 5: The results of the hypothesis no (1)

Instructor s	Mean	Std. Deviation	Test Value=21				Value
			t	f	sig	reality of 0.05	
First hypothesis	30.282	3.39938	24.11	.	significance	Strongly agree	
	1		5	7	001		

The table 5 shows results of the hypothesis no (1) which says: Linguistic difficulties resulting from literal and non-literal meaning in English proverb have direct effects on the translator's ability to find words and equivalents proverbs into Arabic.

Seen from the above, the value of (T. test) calculated (24.115) degree of freedom (53) and table the value of the probability (.001), which means that there's statistical significance from the reality of statistical conclusion of the term that says Linguistic difficulties resulting from literal and non-literal meaning in English proverb have direct effects on the translator's ability to find

words and equivalents when translating proverbs into Arabic Language. It is clear from the reality of statistical inference that subjects approval of this phrase is moderately at the significance level of (0.05). Therefore, the hypothesis is considered true.

Results related to the second hypothesis

Linguistic difficulties are not effectively dealt with by translators in translating proverbs from English into Arabic.

Table 6: The results of the hypothesis no (2)

			Test Value=21					
Instructors	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	f	sig	reality of 0.05	Value	
Second hypothesis	28.7949	3.42398	20.106	7	.001	significance	agree	

The above table 6 shows results of the hypothesis no (2) that says: Linguistic difficulties are not effectively dealt with by translators in translating proverbs from English into Arabic:

Seen from the table above, the value of (T. test) calculated (20.106) degree of freedom (53) and the value of the probability (.001), which means that there's statistical significance from the statistical conclusion reality of the term that says that Linguistic difficulties are not effectively dealt with by translators in translating proverbs from

English into Arabic. It is clear from the reality of statistical inference that the subjects' approval of this phrase is moderately at the significance level of (0.05).

Results related to the third hypothesis

The novice translators lack abilities in utilizing translation methods and procedures to deal with the problem of linguistic difficulties arising when rendering proverbs from English into Arabic.

Table 6: The results of the hypothesis no (3)

			Test Value=24					
Instructors	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	f	Sig	reality Of 0.05	Value	
Third hypothesis	31.8205	4.540 56	15.212	7	.001	significance	agree	

The above table shows results of the hypothesis no (3) which reads: the novice translators lack abilities in utilizing translation methods and procedures to deal with the problem of linguistic difficulties arising when rendering proverbs from English into Arabic:

As seen from the table above, the value of (T. test) calculated (15.212) degree of freedom (53) and the value of the probability (.001), which means that there's statistical significance from the reality of the statistical conclusion of the term that says that the novice translators lack abilities in

utilizing translation methods and procedures to deal with the problem of linguistic difficulties arising when rendering proverbs from English into Arabic. It is clear from the reality of the statistical inference that the subjects' approval of this phrase is moderately at the significance level of (0.05).

Conclusion

In the light of the above-mentioned areas of translation difficulties, the study has shown that the linguistic difficulties which arise when

translating proverbs from English into Arabic are as follow: firstly, the incapability of translating culturally-bound words, sayings and expressions effectively providing irrelevant translation of the proverb. This fact comes in accordance with views conceived by the modern translation theorists such as Catford, (1965), Nida (1964), Savory (1957), Newmark (1988), and Wills (1982) who have understood the fact that translators are not only in need of bilingual competence, but also a good knowledge of the cultures of the languages concerned. Likewise, it agrees with Alsaïdig (2008) who finds that literal translation and lack of linguistic and cultural knowledge in both languages cause problems of fully understanding the intended meaning.

The study concludes that since proverbs are related to different cultural domains, the translator has to look for similar proverb equivalence in the target culture, as Gazala (1995:38) recommends.

The adoption of literal translation indicates inability to follow and apply the ideal methods of translation, improper usage of a strategy or a technique, which renders the meaning, and message clearly and effectively. Also the inability of translators to render word of metaphorical meaning which are utilized to express something but meant something else. Therefore, in rendering proverbs, a translator has to choose a suitable procedure between paraphrasing and literal translation in cases where the appropriate proverb equivalent is not found. This procedure, however, depends on the significance of the specific lexical items that make up the proverbial expression as stated by (Baker, 1992:72).

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the current study, the researcher recommends the following:

Since the culture-base sayings words and expressions seem to be problematic when translating proverbs from English into Arabic, translators are to be exposed to a wider range of reading literature materials in different genres and cultures of both (SL) and (TL) languages, If we took this step, it would greatly enhance their knowledge and awareness in this regard i.e. culture awareness and language competence in general.

The novice translators themselves should perhaps be given much more practical drills and

translation practice in which they could be able to identify and then apply the most appropriate translation methods and procedures according to the text type and language level.

It would be beneficial for translators if Arabic courses in figurative language and style are included when describing and specifying translation courses for them .That would help in producing correct Arabic versions of the translated text when doing translation.

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